

IntelliCampus

Mr. Abhilash L Bhat¹, Anushree G M², Mandara K S³, Manisha G N⁴, Pavithra A S⁵

¹Assistant Professor, ^{2,3,4,5}Under Graduate Student

Dept of Computer Science
and Engineering, K S
Institute of Technology,
Bengaluru, Karnataka.

ABSTRACT: Chatbots, or expert systems, are designed to comprehend and respond to user queries in a conversational manner, much like human interactions. This college chatbot project aims to streamline the academic admission procedure by offering two interaction modes, text and audio, providing a user-friendly experience, especially for parents residing in different locations. The system serves as a platform for students and parents to ask questions and resolve doubts through simple English text messages or audio commands, eliminating the need for physical visits to the inquiry window. In the educational domain, chatbots have become essential for providing intelligent support to users. This paper presents a Chatbot system designed to assist university students in their inquiries. The system's architecture is specifically developed to manage communication and provide accurate responses to student queries, employing artificial intelligence techniques and natural language processing. The experimental implementation of the model verifies its enforceability and efficiency in handling student inquiries effectively. College chatbots, serving as expert systems, understand and respond to user queries in a conversational manner, acting as virtual assistants. This implemented chatbot offers text and audio modes, providing an interactive way of answering through voice messages for a better user experience. The system addresses the challenges faced during the institute's academic admission procedure, particularly for parents in different locations. The goal is to create a platform for students and parents to ask queries and clear doubts through simple English text messages or audio commands, reducing the need for physical visits to the inquiry desk.

Keywords: Chatbot, College chatbot, Artificial intelligence, Natural language processing, Natural language understanding, Pattern matching technique.

I.INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the landscape of artificial intelligence (AI) has witnessed transformative strides, particularly in networking and information technology. These advancements have ushered in a new era, showcasing AI's sophisticated ability to comprehend and engage with human behaviour. One standout achievement is the development of chatbots, also known as talkers or Artificial Conversational Entities. These intelligent agents have not only revolutionized interactions within educational institutions but have become integral to our daily lives. In educational settings, chatbots embedded within administrative systems have redefined how students and faculty interact with institutional services. These chatbots, powered by cutting-edge AI algorithms, adeptly address student queries, providing prompt and accurate responses. Their user-friendly platforms streamline the information-seeking process, eliminating the need for cumbersome searches on institutional websites. With the ability to offer timely and relevant information, these chatbots play a crucial role in keeping students and stakeholders well-informed about institutional affairs, significantly enhancing the overall user experience. Beyond education, AI's integration into daily life has birthed intelligent agents like chatbots, designed for versatile Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). These digital assistants respond to text or voice interactions, utilizing Natural Language Processing (NLP) to simulate a human-like understanding of languages. Chatbots, often termed digital assistants or interactive agents, have found applications not only in entertainment but also in diverse fields such as education, information retrieval, commerce, and e-commerce. The popularity of chatbots is attributed to their platform-agnostic implementations, immediate accessibility without installations, and seamless integration into messaging apps. An exemplary instance is the AI Chatbot, strategically crafted to enhance user-friendliness, reduce student search time, and analyse user requests through advanced AI algorithms. The multifaceted nature of chatbots is explored in academic research, demonstrated through related work, proposed models, experimental results,

and discussions. As technology continues to evolve, the implementation of college chatbots emerges as a pivotal and forward-thinking solution, embodying the synergy between artificial intelligence and human interaction.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- A. A novel Implementation of a Chatbot System using AI and NLP:** This paper discusses the use of chatbots as a conversational user interface, offering an alternative to mainstream options like GUI and web-based interfaces. The chatbot, developed using artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) algorithms, serves as an intelligent system on a college website. It addresses the challenge of finding specific information on a college's website, providing a fast, standard, and informative widget to enhance user experience. The chatbot handles queries related to examination cell, admission, academics, attendance, grade point average, placement cell, and other activities. The aim is to simulate a human conversation, utilizing a language model and computational algorithms. The paper emphasizes the user-friendly interface, efficient search capabilities, and database storage of questions, answers, keywords, and logs. It also introduces an interface for both users and administrators. The goal is to streamline information retrieval for college students and employees, ultimately improving the overall user experience on the college website.
- B. Chatbot for University Related FAQs:** The paper delves into the realm of chatbots, which are artificial intelligence conversational agents designed to mimic human interaction. It highlights their growing importance in various web services, ranging from scientific and entertainment systems to commercial applications and academia. The focus is particularly on developing an interactive chatbot tailored for the university environment, catering to the unique needs and queries of students and parents.

The designed chatbot serves as a virtual assistant capable of handling a diverse range of tasks, from answering general questions to providing specific information related to college admissions and academics. To achieve efficiency in answering queries, the paper employs a combination of Artificial Intelligence Markup Language (AIML) and Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA). AIML is utilized for handling common inquiries and greetings, while LSA comes into play for more intricate service-related questions.

The workflow of the chatbot involves preprocessing input text to standardize it and identify appropriate contexts based on keywords. The system then responds to personal queries, authenticating users and extracting relevant information from the database. Additionally, AIML responses are generated for normal conversational interactions, and LSA is employed for in-depth query analysis and responses related to college-specific information.

The paper outlines the overall workflow, presenting a systematic approach to ensure effective responses to user queries. It also suggests future enhancements by proposing a blend of AIML and LSA. This envisioned combination aims to provide users with a more natural and intuitive interaction experience with the chatbot. The emphasis is on refining patterns and templates to further improve the chatbot's responsiveness to a wide array of general user queries. The conclusion anticipates that this evolution will contribute to an enhanced and more user-friendly chatbot system in the future.

- C. College Enquiry Chat-Bot System:** This paper addresses the implementation of a virtual assistant based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) to handle college-related queries. It emphasizes the growing role of AI in various fields and aims to create a College-Oriented Intelligence machine, specifically designed to respond to students' inquiries. The virtual assistant, acting as a chatbot, utilizes an algorithm to analyze and understand user messages, providing information stored in its database as responses.

The paper discusses the significance of chatbots in online communication and their ability to simulate human behavior. It highlights the challenges of writing rules for various scenarios and introduces the concept of an intellectual chat-bot system for academic activities. The project's purpose includes addressing admission inquiries, providing details on fees, scholarships, department timetables, and required documents. The step-

by-step methodology involves preprocessing queries, fetching keywords, matching them with a knowledge base, and utilizing a database module for additional services.

The system's goal is to assist students in staying updated with college activities, utilizing AI and a knowledgeable database to enhance pattern matching and virtual assistance. The proposed chatbot, developed for the Android system, aims to facilitate communication between humans and machines, reducing the workload on college office staff and enhancing response times to user queries. The methodology incorporates both qualitative and quantitative perspectives, involving literature reviews, expert opinions, focus groups, and content validation for a comprehensive approach.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. *Neural Network Model:*

At the core of the system's intelligence lies a cutting-edge Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) neural network model, representing the pinnacle of artificial intelligence technology. This model is meticulously structured with input, output, and hidden layers, allowing it to process complex data and extract meaningful patterns. Trained using a meticulously pre-processed dataset, which has undergone advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, the neural network is primed to understand and interpret user inputs with exceptional accuracy. Leveraging the Keras Sequential Model, a widely acclaimed framework for building neural networks, the trained model serves as a robust and reliable engine for predicting and generating contextually relevant responses to user queries. Through its intricate architecture and sophisticated training, the neural network empowers the system to engage users in meaningful conversations, offering tailored and insightful interactions that enhance the overall user experience.

The system operates through a meticulously orchestrated series of stages, each contributing to the seamless flow of interaction and response delivery:

- 1) *Processing User Input (Stage 1):*** At the forefront of the system's operation is the pivotal role played by the Natural Language Processing (NLP) unit in handling user inputs. Regardless of whether users submit text or voice-based queries, the system's NLP unit efficiently receives and processes these inputs. This initial stage is crucial as it involves standardizing and parsing user inputs, ensuring consistency and uniformity in the data received. By standardizing inputs, the system can effectively prepare the data for subsequent processing and analysis. This foundational step lays the groundwork for further stages of operation, enabling the system to delve into more advanced techniques for understanding and generating responses to user queries. Thus, the NLP unit serves as the gateway to the system's ability to comprehend and interact with users in a meaningful and coherent manner, ultimately enhancing the overall user experience.
- 2) *Preparing the Trained Model (Stage 2):*** Once the dataset has undergone preprocessing via Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, it undergoes a subsequent phase of refinement aimed at extracting essential features and patterns. This refinement process is critical for distilling the dataset into its most pertinent components, enhancing the neural network model's ability to discern meaningful insights. The processed data, enriched with refined features, are then utilized to train the neural network model. Through this training process, the model hones its capacity to accurately interpret and respond to user queries by learning from the patterns present in the data. Following training, the resulting model is stored and meticulously organized for subsequent use. During interactions with users, this trained model is efficiently loaded, serving as the backbone for generating contextually relevant and accurate responses. In essence, this iterative cycle of preprocessing, refinement, training, and storage forms the foundation of the system's capability to engage users effectively and deliver meaningful interactions through the chatbot interface.

3) **Prediction Process and Response Generation (Stage 3):** In the pivotal stage of user interaction, the system harnesses the power of its trained neural network model to predict and generate responses to user queries with precision. By leveraging the knowledge acquired during training, the system thoroughly analyzes the user input, comparing it against learned patterns and contexts embedded within the dataset. Through this process, the system identifies the most suitable response from its extensive knowledge base, ensuring that the generated response is both accurate and contextually relevant. To further refine the generated response and optimize coherence in the interaction, a sophisticated response selector mechanism comes into play. This mechanism meticulously fine-tunes the generated response, taking into account various factors such as user intent, language nuances, and conversation context. Through the collaborative effort of the trained neural network model and the response selector mechanism, the system delivers responses that are not only accurate but also tailored to meet the specific needs and preferences of the user, thereby enhancing the overall quality of interaction within the chatbot interface.

The College Chatbot System represents a pinnacle of technological innovation, seamlessly integrating AI, NLP, and neural network models to deliver a human-like conversational experience within the college context. Its comprehensive architecture, coupled with advanced features and processes, empowers users to engage effectively while receiving accurate and timely responses tailored to their needs.

IV. DATASETS

```
{
  "intents": [
    {
      "tag": "greeting",
      "patterns": [
        "Hi",
        "How are you",
        "Is anyone there?",
        "Hello",
        "Good day",
        "Whats up",
        "how are ya",
        "hey",
        "whatsup"
      ],
      "responses": [
        "Hello!",
        "Good to see you again!",
        "Hi there, how can I help?"
      ],
      "context_set": ""
    }
  ],
}
```

Fig1: Dataset

A JSON dataset containing comprehensive college information has been curated to facilitate query responses within a chatbot interface. This dataset serves as a repository of data points encompassing various aspects of college life, including academic programs, admissions criteria, campus facilities, extracurricular activities, and more. Structured in JSON format, the dataset organizes information into easily navigable categories, enabling efficient retrieval and presentation of relevant details in response to user queries. By leveraging this dataset, the chatbot can provide accurate and timely responses to inquiries regarding college-related topics, enhancing user experience and satisfaction.

V. METHODOLOGY

The development of college chatbot involves defining objectives, understanding user requirements, selecting a suitable platform, integrating with college systems, and deploying across various channels.

In the depicted use case diagram, the primary actor is the "User," representing individuals interacting with the chatbot. These users engage with the chatbot through a chat interface, sending messages or queries with the expectation of receiving relevant and helpful responses in return. The chatbot's core functionality revolves around understanding user inputs, processing them, and generating appropriate responses based on the user's needs or requests. This includes providing information, answering questions, assisting with tasks, or addressing inquiries. As an artificial intelligence application, the chatbot utilizes natural language processing (NLP) techniques to comprehend user inputs effectively. Once the chatbot processes the user's input, it generates a response tailored to the user's query. This response is then delivered back to the user through the chat interface or communication channel, continuing the conversation and facilitating further interaction. Overall, the chatbot serves as a virtual conversational agent, simulating human-like interaction to provide users with efficient and helpful support.

Fig 2: Use Case Model

Chatbot is a comprehensive endeavour that involves several key steps to ensure effectiveness and user satisfaction.

A. *Defining Objectives and Understanding User Requirements:*

The process commences with a thorough understanding of the objectives behind implementing the chatbot and the specific requirements of the users, including prospective students and parents. This involves identifying the key areas of inquiry, such as admissions, academic programs, career guidance, and support services, to tailor the chatbot's capabilities accordingly.

B. *Preparation of Questions Related to Counselling Process:*

A crucial step in the development process is the meticulous preparation of questions related to the counseling process. This phase involves collaboration with counseling experts to compile a comprehensive set of queries that encompass the diverse needs and concerns of users. These questions serve as the foundation for training the chatbot to provide accurate and relevant responses.

C. Semantic Analysis for Handling Varied Forms of Queries:

To enhance the chatbot's effectiveness, semantic analysis techniques are employed to handle various forms of similar queries. Through natural language processing, the chatbot is trained to decipher the underlying semantic meaning behind different expressions of the same question. This capability ensures that the chatbot can deliver consistent and accurate responses, regardless of how users phrase their queries, thereby enhancing the overall user experience.

D. Capability to Process Questions of Varying Complexity:

The developed solution ensures that the chatbot possesses the versatility to process questions of varying complexity, ranging from simple inquiries to more intricate ones. Whether users seek basic information about admission deadlines or require detailed explanations of academic policies, the chatbot is equipped to comprehend and respond appropriately. This versatility is achieved through an extensive knowledge base and advanced algorithms that enable the chatbot to provide comprehensive support across the counseling spectrum.

E. Execution and Assessment of Conversational Agents Utilizing Diverse Technological Frameworks:

The implementation of chatbot solutions involves the strategic integration of various technologies aimed at optimizing performance and enhancing user experience. Key technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), machine learning algorithms, and potentially deep learning models are leveraged to augment the chatbot's understanding of user intent and context. Through a meticulous comparative analysis of different technologies, the most suitable ones are selected based on criteria such as accuracy, scalability, and compatibility with existing systems.

Below figure illustrates the methodology for developing a chatbot solution. The process begins with the creation of a dataset comprising questions sourced from various social media portals and interactions with students and faculty of a specific technical university. Answers to these questions are obtained from authorized sources within the college.

Subsequently, the following methodology is employed to utilize this dataset and design an effective chatbot:

F. Data Collection and Preparation:

Questions related to the technical university are collected from social media platforms and interactions with stakeholders. Answers to these questions are sourced from authorized sources within the university to ensure accuracy and reliability.

G. Dataset Creation:

The collected questions and corresponding answers are organized into a structured dataset, facilitating efficient processing and analysis.

H. Technology Integration and Analysis:

Various technologies, including NLP, machine learning algorithms, and potentially deep learning models, are integrated into the chatbot solution. A comparative analysis of these technologies is conducted to determine the most suitable ones based on performance metrics such as accuracy, scalability, and ease of integration with existing systems.

I. Chatbot Design and Development:

Based on the selected technologies and the structured dataset, the chatbot is designed and developed to effectively understand user queries and provide relevant responses. Iterative testing and refinement are conducted to ensure the chatbot's accuracy and usability.

J. Deployment and Evaluation:

The developed chatbot solution is deployed across various channels to make it accessible to users. Continuous monitoring and evaluation are performed to assess the chatbot's performance, gather user feedback, and identify areas for improvement.

Fig 3: Chatbot development methodology

The initial stage involves preprocessing raw data, transforming it into a more accessible and efficient format for subsequent processing. This preprocessing also involves normalizing the dataset and reducing the number of features, thereby simplifying the fitting process for each classification model and decreasing overall complexity.

Below, the pre-processing steps are outlined:

A. Lowercasing:

Raw text is converted to lowercase to standardize words and avoid counting multiple variants of the same word separately, ensuring uniformity in processing.

B. Tokenization:

Text is segmented into meaningful elements called tokens, which can represent words, sentences, or other linguistic units, facilitating further analysis and processing.

C. Bag of Words (BoW):

BoW model is utilized to transform words into numerical vectors understandable by neural networks. Two common BoW representations include binary encoding (0s and 1s indicating presence or absence of words) and frequency-based counting (counting occurrences of words). BoW size equals the number of unique root words in the dataset, simplifying data representation for classification models.

D. Stopwords Removal:

Frequently occurring but irrelevant words, known as stopwords (e.g., "a," "the"), are eliminated from the text to reduce noise and improve model accuracy.

Removing stopwords reduces vector space, enhances model performance, and reduces computational overhead during training.

E. Stemming:

Stemming involves stripping prefixes and suffixes from words to reduce them to their root forms.

Words with similar roots are consolidated into a single feature, reducing feature space and improving classifier performance.

For example, words like "likes," "liked," and "liking" are stemmed to their root form "like."

F. Lemmatization:

Lemmatization, similar to stemming, groups words with the same root form.

However, lemmatization considers the context and meaning of words, ensuring that words with different meanings are not incorrectly grouped together.

For instance, words like "went," "going," and "gone" are all lemmatized to "go," despite their different forms, maintaining the semantic integrity of the text.

These pre-processing steps collectively prepare the text data for effective analysis and classification by reducing complexity, noise, and dimensionality while retaining semantic meaning and improving model performance.

After pre-processing next step is to use it for building a model for a chatbot. This is done using a Neural network.

Fig: 4 Structure of a neural network

The neural network framework draws inspiration from the biological neural network found in the human brain. It comprises an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer, forming an artificial neural network. Each artificial neuron within these layers is interconnected, with assigned weights governing the connections.

A Feed Forward Neural Network represents a fundamental neural network type, transmitting information in a unidirectional manner. In contrast, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks utilize recurrent neural networks, facilitating non-linear information flow. LSTMs are particularly suited for sequential or temporally linked data. However, they can be slower and demand substantial high-quality datasets to yield satisfactory results.

The described model operates on a sequence-to-sequence basis, where it progresses layer by layer to generate responses based on past experiences. This approach entails a systematic analysis of input sequences and corresponding outputs, allowing the model to discern patterns and generate contextually relevant replies. While this method typically yields more reliable responses, it may suffer from slower processing times and

inherent limitations. However, by introducing additional layers to the process, the model becomes more adept at handling complex inputs and refining its output. This enhanced depth fosters greater efficiency in response generation, enabling the model to deliver more accurate and nuanced replies. In essence, augmenting the model with additional layers enhances its ability to learn from past interactions and generate responses that better align with user queries and expectations

VI. RESULTS

A. Accuracy:

```
# Compiling the ANN
model.compile(optimizer = 'adam', loss = 'categorical_crossentropy', metrics = ['accuracy'])
# Fitting the ANN model to training set
model.fit(x_train, y_train, batch_size = 10, epochs = 100)
```

```
42/42 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0187 - accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 98/100
42/42 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0180 - accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 99/100
42/42 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0173 - accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 100/100
42/42 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0166 - accuracy: 1.0000
```

The output of training the model for the college chatbot using the collected and formatted data in JSON, along with the Neural network framework, is indicative of highly promising results. Achieving a 100 percent accuracy suggests that the model has successfully learned and comprehensively captured the patterns and nuances present in the dataset. Additionally, the reported loss value of 0.0166 signifies minimal error during the training process, highlighting the model's robustness and efficiency in generalizing from the training data. These outcomes underscore the effectiveness of employing advanced machine learning techniques in developing a sophisticated chatbot system capable of accurately addressing user queries pertaining to college information.

PREDICTED OUTPUT

Fig 5. Output

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In college settings, students and parents often encounter numerous queries regarding aspects like available branches, faculty information, courses, and various other college-related topics. Traditionally, addressing these inquiries involves visiting the college premises or making phone calls, yet the sheer volume of queries can overwhelm college officials, leading to potential miscommunications or delays in response. Consequently, students may resort to unofficial sources such as Quora for information, and navigating through the college website can prove cumbersome and time-consuming. To mitigate these challenges, the primary aim is to consolidate all college data into a single, user-friendly interface, facilitating efficient query resolution for students and faculty alike. This initiative centres on developing a chatbot capable of instantly and efficiently responding to queries by leveraging a database comprising questions, answers, and keywords. For queries without direct answers, the chatbot redirects users to the college website for further information. By implementing such a system, students and faculty can save valuable time otherwise spent on office visits or navigating queues, thereby enhancing overall productivity. The integration of machine learning and a knowledge base is crucial for facilitating seamless interactions between users and the chatbot, necessitating the development of algorithms capable of effectively retrieving relevant information from the database. Through a comprehensive review of prior research papers and surveys, optimal methods for achieving these objectives have been identified and incorporated into the chatbot development process. In the future, integrating ChatGPT into counselling could involve improving emotional understanding, adapting to users' needs, exploring different ways of interacting, protecting privacy, being culturally sensitive, connecting with counselling resources, getting ongoing feedback from users, making it easier to use, handling many conversations at once, and testing to make sure it works well. These changes aim to make ChatGPT better at helping people with counselling, by being more personal, responsive, and welcoming to everyone.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tarun Lalwani, Shashank Bhalotia, Ashish Pal, et al. "Implementation of a Chatbot System using AI and NLP". In: International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer Science & Technology (IJIRCST) Volume- 6, Issue-3 (2018).
- [2] Bhavika R Ranoliya, Nidhi Raghuvanshi, and Sanjay Singh. "Chatbot for university related FAQs". In: 2017 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communications and Informatics (ICACCI). IEEE.2017, pp. 1525–1530.
- [3] Guruswami Hiremath, et.al," Chatbot for education system." In International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology, ISSN: 2454-132X
- [4] Milla T Mutiwokuziva, et.al "A neural-network based chat bot." In 2017 2nd International Conference on and Electronics Systems (ICCES)
- [5] Assistant Prof Ram Manoj Sharma, "Chatbot based College Information System", RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary, ISSN: 2455-3085 (Online), Volume-04, Issue03, March-2019, pp 109-112
- [6] Amey Tiwari, Rahul Talekar, Prof.S.M.Patil, "College Information Chat Bot System", International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science, ISSN 2091-2730, Volume 5, Issue 2, MarchApril, 2017, pp 131-137.
- [7] P.Nikhila, G.Jyothi, K.Mounika, Mr. C Kishor Kumar Reddy and Dr. B V Ramana Murthy on , "Chatbots Using Artificial Intelligence", International Journal of Research and Development, Volume VIII, Issue I, January/2019, ISSN NO:2236-6124, pp 1-12
- [8] Prof.K.Bala, Mukesh Kumar ,Sayali Hulawale, Sahil Pandita, "Chatbot For College Management System Using A.I", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056, p-ISSN: 2395-0072, Volume: 04 Issue: 11 | Nov -2017, pp 2030-2033
- [9] Ms.Ch.Lavanya Susanna, R.Pratyusha, P.Swathi, P.Rishi Krishna, V.Sai Pradeep, "College Enquiry Chatbot", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), e-ISSN: 2395-0056, p-ISSN: 2395-0072, Volume: 07 Issue: 3 Mar 2020 pp 784-788.